

Topic : Dowry:- A Curse for Society

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ABSTRACT:

Dowry, also known as Dahej, is one of the deep-rooted societal ills that has become an obstacle to women's regular lives. Dowry has become a societal norm, which is a major issue for both society and women. The dowry system is the evil that has murdered and disabled countless vulnerable women, forcing some to commit suicide. Dowry is the oldest social malady or sickness on the Indian subcontinent. It has become a terrible social disorder that is profoundly established in people's blood. Many individuals regard dowry as a symbol of social standing and self-recognition. As Mahatma Gandhi has rightly said "Any young man, who makes dowry a condition to marriage, discredits his education and his country and dishonours womanhood". The main goal is to investigate the ills of the Dowry system and its repercussions¹ in India.

¹ An unintended consequence of an event or action, especially an unwelcome one.

INTRODUCTION:

The problem of cruelty against women in Indian society is still present; domestic violence against women in India is rooted in the need for dowry. Dowry can occur in every family, regardless of wealth, bourgeoisie², poverty, education, or uneducated status. When a marriage is set, no one cares how intelligent, homely, or bright the girl is; all that matters is how much money and luxury she will receive at her husband's family. With the passage of time, dowry became an usual element of Indian society, and men began to demand dowry as a right to marry a woman, and dowry became violence against women when the groom's family did not receive enough dowry, resulting in harassment.

According to section 2 of the Dowry Prohibition Act 1961, dowry is defined as "property brought by a woman to her husband at the time of marriage," which includes land, other properties, and valuable securities given or agreed to be given directly or indirectly at the time of marriage. Dowry does not include the return of wedding expenditures.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM:

The dowry system has terrible social and cultural consequences for society as a whole. Women were reduced to a commodity and a source of money by the system. [2] Even if the dowry is paid, the bride is usually abused mentally and physically by her in-laws as their demand for additional payment becomes insatiable (Chirmade 1992). The bride usually commits suicide or is murdered as a result of this abuse.

Dowry persists in India not just because it is difficult to enforce the legislation against it or because the groom's family is extremely demanding, but also because the bride's family continues to tolerate it. Despite broad awareness of the negative implications of dowry and the troubles it causes, it is still considered as a method for the bride to buy happiness (Stone and James, 1995). Many households feel that providing a large dowry will result in the groom's family treating the daughter better. This has further exacerbated³ the situation as the dowry standard has risen, and marriage has become dependent on whether or not the bride's family can reach that dowry requirement.

What is the anti- dowry law in India?

Since 1961, India has had a Dowry Prohibition Act, although the practise of dowry has continued unabated. It is implied that the bride's family will have to give 'gifts' and pay for the groom and his family's quality of living even if it is not explicitly asked.

² Belonging to or characteristic of the middle class, typically with reference to its perceived materialistic values or conventional attitudes.

³ Make (a problem, bad situation, or negative feeling) worse.

The anti-dowry law in India makes dowry illegal. The Dowry Prohibition Act makes it illegal to take or donate dowry in India. The penalty for breaking the anti-dowry law is up to 5 years in prison and a fine of Rs. 15,000 or the value of the dowry given, whichever is higher. Any lady who has been a victim of dowry in India should get legal advice from a dowry lawyer.

Misuse of anti – dowry law

It has become normal practise to employ anti-dowry legislation⁴ to blackmail a husband. The frequency of bogus 498A lawsuits and incidents of anti-dowry legislation abuse has prompted India's Supreme Court to label it "legal terrorism." Because of the law's bias, women have been able to file fraudulent cases against their spouses for reasons such as:

- She wanted to leave the marriage since she couldn't adjust to the new family.
- Using blackmail to get money from the husband.
- To frame her spouse in a fake case and revive her relationship with a man she had previously been involved with or had an extramarital affair with.

If the woman abuses the anti-dowry statute, the husband should engage a dowry lawyer.

Death of Dowry

'Dowry Death' is dealt with in Section 304-B of the Indian Penal Code, 1860. The Dowry Prohibition (Amendment) Act of 1986 placed this new Sec.304-B into the code.

Sec. 304-B is an addition to Sec. 498, which was added to the Code. Following that, Secs. 304-B and 498-A operate as follows:

Section 304-B

1. Where a woman's death is caused by any burns or bodily injury or occurs otherwise than under normal circumstances within seven years of her marriage, and it is shown that she was subjected to cruelty or harassment⁵ by her husband or any relative or her husband for, or in connection with, any demand for dowry, such death shall be called 'Dowry Death,' and such husband or relative shall be deemed to have caused her death.

2. Anyone who commits dowry death faces a minimum sentence of seven years in prison and a maximum sentence of life in prison.

⁴ The process of making or enacting laws.

⁵ Aggressive pressure or intimidation.

HUSBAND OR HIS RELATIVES CRUELTY FOR DOWRY.

Section 498-A

The husband or his family who subject a married lady to cruelty are punished under Section 498-A of the Indian Penal Code. The Criminal Law (Amending) Act of 1983 added the clause to combat⁶ the threat of dowry deaths. By the same act, Section 113-A of the Indian Evidence Act was inserted, which states that when a married lady commits herself within seven years of her marriage, the court may conclude that the husband or his relatives are involved. As a result, it boosts the possibility of a married woman aiding in suicide.

Whoever, being the husband or a relative of the husband of a woman treats such woman to cruelty shall be punished with imprisonment for a time which may exceed to three years and shall also be subjected to fine.” To raise awareness of Dowry and provide legal aid to victims, the State and National Commission for Women, District and State Human Rights Protection Cells, Mahila P.Ss., and Sishu Desks in Police Stations have been established. Due to increased knowledge and publicity by various media and non-governmental groups, a considerable number of women are now coming out to file complaints against dowry-related crimes.”

Stats of dowry in India

Every day, twenty-one dowry fatalities are recorded across the country, yet only 34.7 percent of those charged are convicted⁷.

According to the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), 7,634 women died in the United States in 2015 as a result of dowry harassment. They were either burned alive or forced to commit suicide because of the dowry demand.

According to the data, authorities charged roughly 93.7 percent of those implicated after dowry fatalities were registered, but just 34.7 percent were convicted. Various courts are still hearing the outstanding cases.

According to Delhi Police, till March 15 this year, 31 women died due to dowry harassment.

In the last five years, as many as 715 cases of dowry deaths have been reported in the national Capital and the crime rate have been increasing with every passing year.

Moreover, in Delhi, around 3,877 cases of cruelty by in-laws and husbands have been registered in 2016. Till March 15 this year, as many as 506 such cases have been reported in the city. The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961, prohibits the request, payment or acceptance of a dowry ‘as

⁶ Take action to reduce or prevent (something bad or undesirable).

⁷ Having been declared guilty of a criminal offence by the verdict of a jury or the decision of a judge.

consideration for marriage’, and dowry here is defined as a gift demanded or given as a precondition⁸ for marriage.

According to the Delhi Police, 31 women died as a result of dowry harassment between January and March of this year.

In the last five years, 715 dowry fatalities⁹ have been reported in the national capital, and the crime rate continues to rise with each passing year.

In addition, roughly 3,877 incidences of abuse by in-laws and husbands were reported in Delhi in 2016. There have been 506 similar incidents documented in the city as of March 15 this year. The Dowry Prohibition Act of 1961 outlaws the demand, payment, or acceptance of a dowry “as compensation for marriage,” with dowry defined as a gift required or granted as a condition of marriage.

Graph showing dowry death during 2001- 2010

⁸ A condition that must be fulfilled before other things can happen or be done.

⁹ An occurrence of death by accident, in war, or from disease.

Discussing about the above graph we come to know that situation of women is very bad regarding dowry. More than 6 thousand of dowry death were recorded yearly. This is the main reason why people treat girl's as burden on them. Some of the greedy people do harrasment after marriage due to which they commit suicide or even they murdered by their in law's. In India, 20 women die every day as a result of dowry harassment – either as a result of being murdered or being forced to commit suicide.

CASES RELATED TO DOWRY:-

1. Kamlesh panjiyar vs State of Bihar

Facts of the case: The appellant was married to Jaikali Devi (dead) in this case. Appellant wanted Rs. 40,000 as dowry at the time of marriage, which he received. After their marriage, the appellant demanded a buffalo, which the deceased's family refused to provide. Because his desire was not met, the appellant and his family began tormenting and abusing the deceased. When the deceased's family learned about the circumstance, the deceased's brother went to meet her, but appellant and his family humiliated him. One day, the deceased's brother heard a report about his sister's death. He went to meet appellant's sister and discovered her dead. Her body was riddled with wounds. He went to meet appellant's sister and discovered her dead. Her body was riddled with injuries. The appellant claimed that she died as a result of a rheumatic condition.

Judgement of the case:

The appellant was found guilty and sentenced to ten years in jail by the session court. The court reduced it to 7 years when the appellant filed an appeal in the High Court of Bihar. The Supreme Court confirmed the session court's verdict, stating that direct evidence of causing death was not required under section 304 of the IPC. Cruelty prior to death is sufficient.

2. Reema Agarwal vs anupam and ors (2004) 3 SCC 199

Facts of the case:- In this case, the appellant and the respondent married in January 1998. Her husband and his family, including her mother-in-law, father-in-law, and brother-in-law, tormented her shortly after her marriage over the dowry demand. She was hospitalised one day, and a FIR was filed against all of the defendants. In her testimony to the police officer, she stated that all four attempted to kill her by putting acid in her mouth. It was also revealed that appellant and her spouse were married for the second time. The respondent claimed that sections 498 A and 304 B of the IPC did not apply to them since they were not legally married.

Judgement of the case:-

Because it was both spouses' second marriage, the Session Court acquitted all of the respondents. During the life of his surviving wife, the respondent married the appellant. The provision was construed incorrectly in this case, according to the Supreme Court. Husband refers to a person who has entered into a married relationship and is open to interpretation.

Why the dowry system be stopped?

The new dowry system is causing social concerns. Poor parents are unable to find a groom willing to marry their daughter without a dowry. To marry their daughter, they must take out “Marriage Loans.”

Women’s dowry is becoming a nightmare. Infanticide¹⁰ is becoming more common. There is no other alternative for poor parents. They are purposely killing infant¹¹ girls because they cannot afford to have a girl child. Dowry has resulted in the deaths of almost 8000 women!

Conclusion

Dowry system is good unless and until it is considered as a gift given to the bride by her parents. If the groom’s parents are demanding money to get married as a “Dowry” then that is completely wrong and illegal¹².

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¹⁰ The crime of a mother killing her child within a year of birth.

¹¹ A very young child or baby.

¹² Contrary to or forbidden by law, especially criminal law.